

Potentiometric Study of Some New Chelates of Lanthanum and Yttrium

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METAL chelates of lanthanum and yttrium with 3, 3', 4'-trihydroxyfuchson-2''-sulphonic acid (pyrocatechol violet, abbreviated as PCV), 3, 3''-dibromosulphongallein (Bromopyrogallol red, abbreviated as BPGR) and 1,2-dihydroxy benzene (Pyrocatechol, abbreviated as PC) have been investigated potentiometrically by using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as employed by Irving and Rossotti. The stepwise protonation constants of the ligands and the stepwise formation constants of the metal chelates have been evaluated at constant ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄) and temperature 25°.

The ligands 3, 3', 4'-trihydroxyfuchson-2''-sulphonic acid (Pyrocatechol violet, abbreviated as PCV), 3, 3''-dibromosulphongallein (Bromopyrogallol red, abbreviated as BPGR) and 1,2-dihydroxy benzene (Pyrocatechol, abbreviated as PC) are well known chelating ligands and form coloured chelates with many cations. A survey of the literature revealed that no work has been reported on potentiometric study of lanthanum and yttrium chelates of these ligands. Recently germanium, vanadium(IV), uranium(VI), thorium(IV) chelates of PCV, nickel, cobalt, tungsten and rare earth metal chelates of BPGR and gallium, indium chelates of PC have been studied using spectrophotometric method¹⁻⁵. In the present communication lanthanum and yttrium chelates of these ligands have been investigated potentiometrically using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique⁶.

Experimental

Materials: Solutions of PC (E. Merck) and PCV (AR, BDH) were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts in double distilled water and the solution of BPGR (E. Merck) was prepared in 40% ethanol aqueous media. Lanthanum chloride (AR, BDH) and yttrium chloride (E. Merck) were dissolved in double distilled water. The solutions were estimated gravimetrically by precipitating the metal oxalate and subsequent ignition and weighing as metal oxides. The solutions of required strength were then prepared by suitable dilution. An E. Merck sample of sodium hydroxide was dissolved in double distilled water in a pyrex flask. The layer of carbon dioxide on the sodium hydroxide pellets was washed away previously. The solution was standardised potentiometrically against a standard oxalic acid solution. The stock solution was prepared by suitable dilution. The stock solution of perchloric acid was prepared by diluting AR, BDH sample to required concentration and this was titrated potentiometrically against standard alkali solution. An AR, BDH sample of sodium perchlorate was dissolved in double distilled water to make the stock solution of strength 0.1 M.

Apparatus: A Leeds Northrup pH meter and accessories having glass and calomel electrode assembly were employed in the present investigations, the glass electrode was designed as to cover the entire pH range. The calomel electrode (supplied with the instrument) was replenished with saturated potassium chloride solution (AR, BDH). The pH indicator was calibrated with the buffer solution supplied with the instrument before starting a titration and the calibration was checked again after completion of the titration. A magnetic stirrer was used for stirring the solution during the titration.

Conditions of study: The experiments in the present investigations were performed in an atmosphere of nitrogen gas which was bubbled through the solution. pH measurements were carried out at 25°C using an ultrathermostat bath. The ionic strength of the mixture was kept 0.1 M perchlorate ion by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. The total volume of the mixtures was kept 50 ml,

Procedure: The following three mixtures (a), (b) and (c) were prepared for each system and titrated against standard alkali using Bjerrum-Calvin⁶ pH-titration technique.

- 5 ml perchloric acid + 5 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M) + 40 ml water.
- 5 ml perchloric acid + 5 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M) + 25 ml ligand + 15 ml water.
- 5 ml perchloric acid + 5 ml sodium perchlorate (1.0 M) + 25 ml ligand + 5 ml metal + 10 ml water.

The ratio of metal reagent concentration was kept 1 : 5 in order to satisfy the highest coordination number of the metal. The above three mixtures were titrated separately by adding standard sodium hydroxide progressively with constant stirring and the pH values were recorded from the pH meter. The perchloric acid concentration in PCV and BPGR systems was 0.0119 M and in PC system was 0.0496 M. The concentrations of the ligands PC, PCV and BPGR are fixed at 0.001 M, 0.005 M and 0.005 M respectively. The lanthanum and yttrium concentration for the PC, PCV and BPGR systems are fixed at 0.002 M, 0.001 M and 0.001 M respectively. The mixtures in case of PCV, BPGR and PC systems were titrated against 0.5382 M, 0.4730 M and 0.3510 M NaOH respectively.

Results and Discussion

The proton ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}_A$ (average number of protons associated

Fig. 1. Proton-Ligand Formation Curves of the Ligands
A : PCV ; B : BPGR ; C : PC.

with a ligand) values against pH . The $\bar{n}_A$ values are obtained from Irving-Rossotti⁷ computational methods. The proton ligand formation curve of PCV (Fig. 1, curve A) indicates clearly the liberation of two protons upto pH 7.5. The liberation of third proton could not be observed, however, it could be possible to evaluate the value of $\log K_1^H$ with the help of equation $\log K_1^H = 2 pH (\bar{n}_A = 1.0) - pH (\bar{n}_A = 1.5)$. In case of BPGR, proton-ligand formation constants corresponding to $\bar{n}_A = 1.5, 2.5$ and 3.5 were directly obtained from the formation curve (Fig. 1, curve B) and the formation constant corresponding to $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ could not be calculated because the minimum $\bar{n}_A$ value is 1.369 at pH 10.6. From the proton ligand formation curve (Fig. 1, curve C) for PC the values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ were obtained directly by interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ values. The proton ligand stability constants of the ligands are recorded in table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS.

Ligand	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_3^H$	$\log K_4^H$	$\log \beta^H$
PCV	9.50	7.50	2.70	—	19.70
BPGR	—	10.73	9.00	3.80	23.53
PC	11.145	9.255	—	—	20.40

The metal-ligand formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL are shown in Figure 2. La^{3+} -PCV chelate formation curve (Fig. 2, curve A) is incomplete in the lower half portion and the maximum value of $\bar{n}$ reaches little more than 1.5. The curve is quite symmetrical. Value of $\log K_2$ is directly obtained from the curve and of $\log K_1$ is obtained from equation $\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$. Mid point method could not be applied due to limitations, however, the method of interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values was applicable.

The nature of formation curve of Y^{3+} -PCV (Fig. 2, Curve B) chelate is exactly the same as in La^{3+} -PCV chelate with a slight difference in the range of $\bar{n}$ values. Method of interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ and interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values have been employed as in the case of La^{3+} -PCV chelate.

The formation curve of La^{3+} -BPGR (Fig. 2, curve C) and Y^{3+} -BPGR (Fig. 2, curve D) chelates are incomplete in the lower half portion. The Y^{3+} -BPGR curve minimum reaches $\bar{n} = 1.0$ and nature of the curve below $\bar{n} = 1.0$ is not known, hence, neither mid point nor interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values method could be applied. From the formation curves of both the chelates only one formation constant corresponding to $\bar{n} = 1.5$ could be determined. The value of $\log K_1 K_2$ could be determined from the equation $\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$.

The formation curve of La^{3+} -PC chelate (Fig. 2, curve E) extends from $\bar{n} = 1.0$ to 2.5. Values of $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$, therefore, may be read from the curve

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand formation curves : A : La^{3+} -PCV ; B : Y^{3+} -PCV ;
C : La^{3+} -BPGR ; D : Y^{3+} -BPGR ; E : La^{3+} -PC ; F : Y^{3+} -PC.

directly corresponding to $\bar{n}=1.5$ and 2.5 respectively. Value of $\log K_1$ have been obtained from equation $\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$.

$\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$ and value of $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ being directly read corresponding to $\bar{n}=1.5$ and 2.5 respectively. Mid point method was also applied and values of $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ could be determined.

The formation curve of Y^{3+} -PC chelate (Fig. 2, curve F) is also incomplete in the lower portion and the value of $\log K_1$ is obtained from equation

The stepwise metal ligand stability constants of all the chelates investigated are recorded in table 2.

TABLE 2—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES $\mu=0.1 M (\text{NaClO}_4)$; TEMP. 25°

System	Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta$
La^{3+} -PCV	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	18.50	4.30	—	22.80
	Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values	14.44	7.89	—	22.33
Y^{3+} -PCV	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	19.40	8.80	—	28.20
	Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values	15.85	12.35	—	28.20
La^{3+} -BPGR	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	18.24	15.12	—	33.36
Y^{3+} -BPGR	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	24.92	15.00	—	39.92
La^{3+} -PC	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	15.52	9.90	5.70	31.12
Y^{3+} -PC	Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values	13.65	10.45	8.50	32.60
	Mid point	—	10.45	8.35	—

Examining the $\log \beta$ values of La^{3+} and Y^{3+} chelates of these ligands it is found that for Y^{3+} chelate, $\log \beta$ is always higher than La^{3+} chelate.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C. S. I. R., New Delhi for financial assistance to R. L. K.

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